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Gravity is just a Spin because of Thermodynamics

Sanat Mohanty

January 2026

Just like angular momentum happens in the case of any ordinary object because of a Spin. Similarly Spin of each particle leads to Gravity in an object. A heated object will have fluctuating gravity, which will fluctuate exactly in correlation with the heat waves from that object.

The detailed equations are classified under SIU. and can never be disclosed.

References

- [1] Mohanty, S. (2025). *Vector Spin of subatomic particles and Antigravity*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17056230>
- [2] Mohanty, S. (2025). *Quantum Gravity*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14750716>